

Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT and Longitudinal CT: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT and Longitudinal CT

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

autoPET/CT IV

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Positron Emission Tomography / Computed Tomography (PET/CT) and CT are an integral part of the diagnostic workup for various malignant solid tumor entities. Currently, response assessment for cancer treatment is performed by radiologists (i.e. human observers) on consecutive PET/CT or CT scans through the detection of changes in tumour size and distribution using standardised criteria. Despite the highly time-consuming nature of this manual task, only unidimensional (diameter) evaluations of a subset of tumour lesions are used to assess tumour dynamics. Additional quantitative evaluation of PET information would potentially allow for more precise and individualized diagnostic decisions. Besides the risk of inter-observer variability, the manual approach only extracts a diminutive proportion of the morphologic tumour data derived from images, thereby neglecting valuable, significant, and prognostic information.

Automation of tumour detection and segmentation as well as longitudinal evaluation may enable faster and more comprehensive information and data extraction. However, automated solutions for this task are lacking. AI-based approaches, using deep-learning models, may be an appropriate way to address lesion detection and segmentation in whole-body hybrid imaging (PET/CT and CT) to compensate workload and time pressure during radiological readings. So far, most AI solutions analyse isolated scans at single time points, and/or from a single imaging modality and thus information from preliminary or additional examinations is excluded. Moreover, methods are often prone to specialize to specific imaging conditions (imaging scanner, lesion phenotype, PET tracer, and so on) rendering it a challenge to generalize for different imaging scenarios. In addition, the necessity or potential benefit of integrating human experts in the training and/or inference loop is not yet explored in this setting.

In the first run of the autoPET challenge (autoPET I at MICCAI 2022) we provided training and test data from

University Hospital Tübingen (UKT) and LMU Hospital (LMU) as well as a baseline model for automated lesion segmentation on whole-body Fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) PET/CT data. The challenge results demonstrated the feasibility of accurate lesion segmentation. In the second edition of the autoPET challenge (autoPET II at MICCAI 2023) we shifted our focus towards evaluating algorithmic robustness across different environments. This involved introducing a new test set comprising samples from various sites, utilizing different tracers and presenting diverse pathologies. We also relaxed constraints on using external and additional data. The challenge results revealed a substantial decline in performance, highlighting the critical need for the development of robust algorithms. Based on these insights, the scope of the third edition of the autoPET challenge (autoPET III at MICCAI 2024) was to achieve multitracer and multicenter generalization of automated lesion segmentation. To this end, we provided participants access to a second, large Prostate-Specific Membrane Antigen (PSMA) whole-body PET/CT training dataset. The challenge results demonstrated good efforts towards PET tracer (FDG and PSMA) generalization with an increased usage of appropriate data processing pipelines (data-centric approach) and pre-trained or foundational models. A key challenge that remained was accurate lesion detection under changing scenarios, i.e. keeping low false positives and false negatives. The specific difficulty lies in the facts that not only tumor lesions but also healthy organs (e.g. the brain) can have significant uptake. Hence, lesions cannot be well delineated against their surroundings, and in addition individual tumor instances cannot be separated from a cluster of tumor lesions.

We propose to focus the fourth challenge autoPET/CT IV on lesion segmentation within a clinical-realistic setting of single-staging PET/CT and longitudinal CT monitoring. For this purpose we will investigate an interactive human-in-the-loop scenario to identify the potential benefits, requirements and necessities for hybrid AI methods. Algorithms are provided with varying levels of annotations with the aim to investigate the model conditioning on label information for two imaging scenarios: single-staging PET/CT and longitudinal CT. This concept aligns closely with real-world clinical workflows, enabling users to specify particular lesion instances for precise segmentation and longitudinal tracking over time. To this end, we provide a third, large longitudinal CT training dataset of melanoma patients under therapy. We allow the submission of data-centric solutions (using the provided baselines), integration and interaction with foundation models, using/extending pre-trained algorithms, or the developments of novel algorithms.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

PET/CT, CT, tumor, segmentation, interactive segmentation

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The challenge addresses a clinical realistic scenario to foster the translation of algorithms into clinical workflows. For this purpose we investigate an interactive segmentation where expert users provide coarse annotations on a few (but not necessarily all) lesions. In addition, we pair the PET/CT lesion staging with a longitudinal CT monitoring under therapy. We expect algorithms to cope with lesion detection under existence/absence of molecular PET information and in a longitudinal setting, i.e. tumor segmentation in baseline and follow-up scan to

pave the way for a lesion assessment under therapy. We provide a new large training database of longitudinal CT imaging data. We investigate the performance for varying levels of user input (none to multiple clicks per lesion) and under different input modalities (PET/CT vs. CT), allow data-centric approaches, and enable the usage as well as interaction with foundation models utilizing/handling this auxiliary information.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The tasks will handle lesion segmentation for whole-body hybrid imaging for a single-staging PET/CT (Task 1) or a longitudinal CT screening (Task 2). In Task 1, we study an interactive human-in-the-loop segmentation scenario and investigate the impact of varying degrees of label information (none to multiple clicks per lesion and background) on the segmentation performance. In Task 2, we explore the segmentation performance to detect lesions in a follow-up scan if provided with a lesion segmentation in the baseline scan together with or without clicks of the lesions in the follow-up scan. All public available data and (pre-trained) models (including foundation models) are allowed. Participants can either develop a novel method to address the varying degrees of label information (Task 1: none to multiple dots per lesion and background; Task 2: baseline segmentation with/without lesion center in follow-up scan) or input (PET/CT or multiple scan time points of CT) and/or focus on data-centric approaches, i.e. development on pre- and post-processing pipelines. We encourage the usage of registration algorithms for Task 2, but it is not mandatory. Time points and/or imaging modality inputs can be treated individually or jointly. The aim is to develop robust lesion segmentation methods that work under varying inputs (imaging modality: PET/CT vs. CT, time points: single-staging vs. longitudinal) and for varying levels of human-annotated information. We evaluate the performance over increasing manual annotated information to assess the efficacy of tumour detection.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

50 participants in the session (challenge participants and interested attendees) with a full discussion about the outcomes and future prospectives of machine learning for hybrid imaging.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect ~25 final submissions based on the previous challenges.

Final submissions: 21 (AutoPET I), 18 (AutoPET II), 21 (AutoPET III)

Registered participants: 273 (AutoPET I), 346 (AutoPET II), 612 (AutoPET III).

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We aim to summarize the design, proposed methods and results of the challenge in a manuscript to be submitted to a peer-reviewed scientific journal in the field of medical image analysis. To this end, we aim to invite the best performing participants to contribute by describing their methods and experiences. Furthermore, we aim to make the code of the best performing methods publicly available for the purpose of reproduction of results and further research.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

grand-challenge.org is used as an online platform: NVIDIA T4 GPU (16 GB VRAM) with 8 CPUs and a max memory of 30 GB. Appropriate storage is associated with the deployed virtual machines.

TASK 1: PET/CT lesion segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Positron Emission Tomography / Computed Tomography (PET/CT) and CT are an integral part of the diagnostic workup for various malignant solid tumor entities. Currently, response assessment for cancer treatment is performed by radiologists (i.e. human observers) on consecutive PET/CT or CT scans through the detection of changes in tumour size and distribution using standardised criteria. Despite the highly time-consuming nature of this manual task, only unidimensional (diameter) evaluations of a subset of tumour lesions are used to assess tumour dynamics. Additional quantitative evaluation of PET and CT information would potentially allow for more precise and individualized diagnostic decisions. Besides the risk of inter-observer variability, the manual approach only extracts a diminutive proportion of the morphologic tumour data derived from images, thereby neglecting valuable, significant, and prognostic information.

Automation of tumour detection and segmentation as well as longitudinal evaluation may enable faster and more comprehensive information and data extraction. However, automated solutions for this task are lacking. AI-based approaches, using deep-learning models, may be an appropriate way to address lesion detection and segmentation in whole-body imaging (PET/CT and CT) to compensate workload and time pressure during radiological readings. So far, most AI solutions analyse isolated scans at single time points, and/or from a single imaging modality and thus information from preliminary or additional examinations is excluded. Moreover, methods are often prone to specialize to specific imaging conditions (imaging scanner, lesion phenotype, PET tracer, and so on) rendering it a challenge to generalize for different imaging scenarios. The necessity or potential benefit of integrating human experts in the training and/or inference loop was also not yet explored in this setting.

We propose to focus the fourth challenge autoPET/CT IV on lesion segmentation within a clinical-realistic setting of single-staging PET/CT and longitudinal CT monitoring. For this purpose we will investigate an interactive human-in-the-loop scenario. Algorithms are provided with varying levels of annotations with the aim to investigate the model conditioning on label information. In addition to our two previously published PET/CT datasets, we provide a third, large longitudinal CT training dataset of melanoma patients under therapy. We allow the submission of data-centric solutions (using the provided baselines), integration and interaction with foundation models, using/extending pre-trained algorithms (publicly available), or the developments of novel algorithms.

We set two tasks: Task 1 focuses on PET/CT lesion segmentation in a multi-tracer and multi-center imaging setting - similar to the previous iterations of the autoPET challenge. This time, we study an interactive human-in-the-loop segmentation scenario and investigate the impact of varying degrees of label information (none to multiple clicks per lesion and background) on the segmentation performance.

Task 2 focuses on lesion segmentation in a follow-up CT scan for a given lesion segmentation in the baseline CT. We investigate the segmentation performance in the novel provided CT database - similar to autoPET I - for with

and without provided center lesion click in the follow-up CT scan. Algorithms will be evaluated for their performance with the number of required user interactions: none to single (Task 2)/multiple (Task 1) clicks.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

PET/CT, PSMA, FDG, Tumor, Segmentation, Detection, Robustness

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Thomas Küstner (University Hospital Tübingen)

Sergios Gatidis (University Hospital Tübingen)

Ornela Megne (University Hospital Tübingen)

Michael Ingrisich (LMU Hospital Munich)

Matthias Fabritius (LMU Hospital Munich)

Jakob Dextl (LMU Hospital Munich)

Katharina Jeblick (LMU Hospital Munich)

Andreas Mittermeier (LMU Hospital Munich)

Balthasar Schachtner (LMU Hospital Munich)

Theresa Stüber (LMU Hospital Munich)

Clemens Cyran (LMU Hospital Munich)

Zdravko Marinov (KIT Karlsruhe)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Küstner

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Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event as open call challenge

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge website will be opened on grand-challenge (similar to the previous challenges: autoper.grand-challenge.org)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic, Interactive

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We foresee the following awards for the best submissions in

Category 1: Lesion segmentation in PET/CT

1st Place: 1,500 €

2nd Place: 1,000 €

3rd Place: 500 €

In the event of a tie the aggregate prize allocated for the tied positions shall be combined and equitably divided among the participants who share the identical ranking.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submissions will be reported in the leaderboard. Participating teams can opt out of publication of their results in the leaderboard. Prize-winning methods will be announced publicly as part of a scientific session at the MICCAI annual meeting.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The prize-winning teams will be invited to contribute to draft and submit a manuscript describing the methods and results of the challenge in a peer-reviewed journal. The first and last author of the prize-winning submissions will be also listed as authors of this planned manuscript. The participating teams may publish their own results separately after coordination to avoid significant overlap with the challenge paper.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be accepted as Docker containers according to the technical requirements of grand-challenge.org. Submission details will be published at the time point of challenge announcement.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

In order to enable participants to assess the technical compatibility of their to-be-submitted algorithm, we will provide information on successful algorithm deployment upon submission. To this end, the submitted algorithms will be applied to a small number of test data ensuring technical compatibility. This will allow participants to resubmit their algorithms in case of technical failure.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge announcement and release of training cases: 03/2025

Registration: starting 04/2025

Submission deadline: 09/2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

For the already released FDG PET/CT dataset: The ethics committee of the University Hospital Tuebingen was consulted regarding anonymized publication of training data. Ethical approval was obtained for the anonymized training database.

For the already released PSMA PET/CT dataset: The challenge dataset will be released in an anonymized fashion on the cancer imaging archive (TCIA), following the rigorous and well-established de-identification approach of TCIA. The institutional data security and privacy review board has approved the de-identification approach, and the institutional review board has waived the need for informed consent and approved the publication of the anonymized dataset (Ethics Committee, Medical Faculty, LMU Munich).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code for algorithm evaluation together with a script for standardized user interaction simulation and pre-simulated clicks will be available at the time point of challenge submission on:
www.github.com/lab-midas/autoPETCTIV

We will furthermore provide two trained baseline models and the code for creating the grand-challenge Docker containers.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Publication of algorithm code will be a prerequisite for award eligibility. To this end, code will need to be published on a publicly accessible repository of the teams choice within a week after submission deadline.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge is an initiative of the Radiology Departments of the University Hospitals of Tuebingen and LMU together with the European Society of Radiology (ESR) and the European Society for Hybrid, Molecular and Translational Imaging (ESHI-MT). We have secured funding for this challenge at BMBF (German Federal Ministry of Education and Research). We aim to additionally seek funding for this challenge from major companies in the field of medical imaging and data analysis. So far, no concrete sponsoring has been agreed on. Test cases and labels will only be available to a limited number of colleagues involved in organizing this challenge at the participating institutions.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD,Research,Screening,Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction

- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection, Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of patients undergoing FDG and PSMA PET/CT examinations in an oncologic context for diagnosis, staging, or therapy response assessment, from multiple imaging sites.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The FDG PET/CT cohort comprises 1014 cases of 501 patients diagnosed with histologically proven malignant melanoma, lymphoma, or lung cancer, along with 513 negative control patients. The PSMA cohort includes pre- and/or post-therapeutic PET/CT images of male individuals with prostate carcinoma, encompassing images with (537) and without PSMA-avid tumor lesions (60). Notably, the training datasets exhibit distinct age distributions: the FDG PET/CT (UKT) cohort spans 570 male patients (mean age: 60y; std: 16y) and 444 female patients (mean age: 58y; std: 16y), whereas the PSMA PET/CT (LMU) cohort tends to be older, with 597 male patients (mean age: 71y; std: 8y). Additionally, there are variations in imaging conditions between the FDG (UKT) and PSMA (LMU) cohorts, particularly regarding the types and number of PET/CT scanners utilized for acquisition. The PSMA (LMU) dataset was acquired using three different scanner types (Siemens Biograph 64, Siemens Biograph 20 mCT and GE Discovery 690), whereas the FDG (UKT) dataset was acquired using a single scanner (Siemens Biograph mCT). Additional information about the PET/CT imaging protocols is provided in the section "Data acquisition details".

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All PET/CT data within this challenge have been acquired on state-of-the-art PET/CT scanners using standardized protocols following international guidelines. CT as well as PET data are provided as 3D volumes consisting of stacks of axial slices.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information will be provided regarding the image data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Age, sex, diagnosis

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target and challenge cohort depict whole-body PET/CT imaging. Usually, the scan range of these examinations extends from the skull base to the mid-thigh level. If clinically relevant, scans can be extended to cover the entire body including the entire head and legs/feet. PSMA PET/CT training volumes do not include the head.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target structures of the to-be-developed algorithms are FDG- and PSMA-avid malignant tumors (i.e. primary tumors and metastases).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

PET/CT data were acquired on state-of-the-art PET/CT scanners (Siemens Biograph mCT, Siemens Biograph 64, GE Discovery 690).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Training data:

FDG dataset: Patients fasted at least 6 h prior to the injection of approximately 350 MBq 18F-FDG. Whole-body PET/CT images were acquired using a Biograph mCT PET/CT scanner (Siemens, Healthcare GmbH, Erlangen,

Germany) and were initiated approximately 60 min after intravenous tracer administration. Diagnostic CT scans of the neck, thorax, abdomen and pelvis (200 reference mAs; 120 kV) were acquired 90 sec after intravenous injection of a contrast agent (90-120 ml Ultravist 370, Bayer AG) or without contrast agent (in case of existing contraindications). PET Images were reconstructed iteratively (three iterations, 21 subsets) with Gaussian post-reconstruction smoothing (2 mm full width at half-maximum). Slice thickness on contrast-enhanced CT was 2 or 3 mm.

PSMA dataset: Examinations were acquired on different PET/CT scanners (Siemens Biograph 64, Siemens Biograph 20 mCT and GE Discovery 690). The imaging protocol mainly consisted of a diagnostic CT scan from the skull base to the mid-thigh using the following scan parameters: reference tube current exposure time product of around 140 mAs (mean); tube voltage of 100kV or 120 kV for most cases, slice thickness of 2.5 - 5 mm. Intravenous contrast enhancement was used in most studies, except for patients with contraindications. The whole-body PSMA-PET scan was acquired on average around 71 minutes after intravenous injection of 246 MBq 18F-PSMA (mean, 369 studies) or 214 MBq 68Ga-PSMA (mean, 228 studies), respectively. The PET data was reconstructed with attenuation correction derived from corresponding CT data using standard, vendor-provided image reconstruction algorithms (e.g. an ordered-subset expectation maximization (OSEM) algorithm) with a slice thickness ranging from 3 - 5 mm (mean: 3.5 mm).

Test data: Test data will be drawn in part (50%) from the same sources and distributions as the training data. The other part will be drawn crosswise from other centers, i.e. PSMA from Tuebingen (25%) and FDG from LMU (25%). At this moment we will not disclose details of the test data as we aim to avoid fine-tuning of algorithms to the test data domain. The distribution of test data will be made public after the challenge deadline.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data were acquired from two large university hospitals (UKT, LMU).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data were acquired by specialized teams consisting of radiologists, nuclear medicine physicians, and technologists. Manual segmentation of tumor lesions was performed by two radiologists with experience in hybrid imaging.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).

- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case (training or test case) consists of one 3D whole-body PET volume, one corresponding 3D whole-body CT volume and one 3D binary mask of manually segmented tumor lesions of the size of the PET volume. CT and PET were acquired simultaneously on a single PET/CT scanner in one session; thus PET and CT are anatomically aligned up to minor shifts due to physiological motion. A pre-processing script for resampling the PET and CT to the same matrix size will be provided.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training cases: 1014 FDG PET/CT studies and 597 PSMA PET/CT studies.

Test cases: 200 (50 FDG PET/CT LMU, 50 FDG PET/CT UKT, 50 PSMA PET/CT LMU, 50 PSMA PET/CT UKT).

Challenge participants are free to use additional external training data or pre-trained models as long as these are publicly available. If additional labels are generated in this process, these should be made publicly available by the participants after the challenge. The use of additional training data or models should be reported.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The number of training cases is a trade-off between the effort of manual lesion segmentation and the necessity for sufficient training data. To our knowledge this is the largest publicly available labeled whole-body PET/CT data set for FDG and PSMA tracers.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All training cases are drawn from two hospitals: University Hospital Tuebingen (UKT), University Hospital Munich (LMU).

Test cases are split in four subgroups: 50 FDG PET/CT LMU, 50 FDG PET/CT UKT, 50 PSMA PET/CT LMU, 50 PSMA PET/CT UKT

The rationale behind this selection of test cases is to assess the robustness of algorithms and to cross-evaluate the effects of center and tracer.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Data of 1017 cases (autoPET I + II) and 597 cases (autoPET III) were previously released for trainings of the autoPET challenge series. 25% new test cases will be compiled in this proposed challenge to reflect different clinical scenarios.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All data were manually annotated by two radiologists with experience in hybrid imaging. To this end, tracer-avid tumor lesions were manually segmented on the PET image data using dedicated software.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The following annotation protocol was defined:

Step 1: Identification of tracer-avid tumor lesions by visual assessment of PET and CT information together with the clinical examination reports.

Step 2: Manual free-hand segmentation of identified lesions in axial slices.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

FDG PET/CT training and test data from UKT was annotated by a Radiologist with >10 years of experience in hybrid imaging and experience in machine learning research.

FDG PET/CT test data from LMU was annotated by a radiologist with 9 years of experience in hybrid imaging.

PSMA PET/CT training and test data from the LMU as well as PSMA PET/CT test data from UKT was annotated by a single reader and reviewed by a radiologist with 5 years of experience in hybrid imaging.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For training and test data, original DICOM files will be anonymized and provided. In addition, scripts for conversion to the NIfTI format, for conversion of PET data from original image units (activity count) to standardized uptake values, and for resampling the PET and CT to the same matrix size will be provided.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

One relevant possible error source for image annotation is the uncertainty for whether a tracer-avid lesion is actually malignant as this cannot always be determined by PET/CT alone. For experienced readers and regarding the tumor entities chosen in this challenge, a rough estimate of false classification of lesions in this sense is about 5-10%. The second relevant possible error source is the uncertainty of defining lesion boundaries, especially on PET data that have low intrinsic resolution. The difference in segmentation volumes can range from 5-30%.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

A further potential error source are image artifacts in PET and/or CT that may result in altered image properties.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will use a combination of 6 metrics reflecting the aims and specific challenges for the task of PET/CT lesion detection and segmentation, that are formed of three basic measures:

- a) Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) of segmented lesions (equal to F1 Score).
- b) False positive volumes (FPV): Volume of false positive connected components that do not overlap with positives.
- c) False negative volumes (FNV): Volume of false negative connected components that do not overlap with true positives.

resulting in:

- 1) DSC @last: Interaction Efficacy of DSC at last interactive segmentation step.
- 2) FPV @last: Interaction Efficacy of FPV at last interactive segmentation step.
- 3) FNV @last: Interaction Efficacy of FNV at last interactive segmentation step.
- 4) AUC-DSC: Interaction Utilization as Area under the curve for DSC
- 5) AUC-FPV: Interaction Utilization as Area under the curve for FPV
- 6) AUC-FNV: Interaction Utilization as Area under the curve for FNV

DSC, FPV, and FNV will be evaluated iteratively over 11 interactive segmentation steps. In each step, an additional standardized and pre-simulated tumor (foreground) and background click, represented as a set of 3D coordinates, will be provided alongside the input image. This process will progress incrementally from 0 clicks to the full allocation of 10 tumor and 10 background clicks per image.

Metrics 1-3 assess the final segmentation quality achieved after incorporating all clicks in the last (11th) interactive segmentation iteration. It reflects the performance of the model in producing accurate annotations after completing the full interaction process.

Metrics 4-6 evaluate the AUC for DSC, FPV, and FNV based on the model's intermediate predictions after each interactive segmentation step. The AUC is calculated using the trapezoidal rule, where the x-axis represents the interactive segmentation step (0 to 10) and the y-axis represents the corresponding metric value at each step. This metric quantifies how efficiently a model utilizes the additional information in the form of clicks to achieve a clinically relevant segmentation, measuring how quickly accurate annotations are produced as user clicks are incrementally added.

In case of test data that do not contain positives (no lesions), only metric 2 will be used. For such volumes without tumors, we will also only provide background clicks for all interaction steps.

- b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The overarching objective of the present challenge is to develop approaches for detecting and segmenting tracer-avid tumor lesions. We hypothesize that such automated methods could shift the clinical evaluation of PET/CT imaging in these patients towards a more quantitative approach, which may better support and inform clinical decision-making. While the impact of such a quantitative approach on clinical decision-making is far beyond the scope of the present challenge, we have devised our metrics for the challenge to reflect the critical aspect of PET/CT tumor detection under various levels of user interaction/segmentation. It can be expected that some simplistic annotations are available, or can be provided by the user to adjust the algorithm performance. We are interested in exploring the algorithm's dependency on such information and how additional label information could potentially improve the performance.

The post-challenge analysis of the previous iterations of the autoPET challenge showed that the three basic measures (DSC, FPV, FNV) provide a comprehensive summary description of algorithm performance in terms of segmentation accuracy. In addition, these measures have been used and validated in the previous iterations of the challenge, hence enabling a direct comparison of the proposed challenge with previous iterations. The Dice score will be used as a measure of overall segmentation performance. False positive and false negative volumes are used to reflect the specific challenges of PET lesion segmentation: avoiding segmentation of physiological uptake and detecting small tumor lesion

Ad 1-3) Interaction efficacy assesses the quality of the final segmentation achieved after a predefined annotation budget, such as a fixed number of user clicks. It ensures that the model can deliver high-quality results within a practical and constrained amount of user interaction. This is crucial for real-world usability, where the ability to produce accurate and clinically meaningful segmentations without exceeding a reasonable annotation effort can significantly enhance workflow efficiency and reduce the burden on clinicians. By focusing on the final outcome, interaction efficacy directly measures the practical success of the interactive segmentation process.

Ad 4-6) Interaction Utilization measures how efficiently a model utilizes the provided clicks to achieve a clinically feasible segmentation during a click-based interactive loop. Efficiency is a critical factor in real-world applications, where reducing the time and effort required for annotation and inference directly impacts the practicality of the approach. This is especially significant in the context of whole-body PET/CT images, where lesions can be scattered across multiple body regions. Such cases make manual annotation an exceptionally labor-intensive task, emphasizing the need for a model that can rapidly and accurately refine segmentations with minimal user input, such as a fixed budget of clicks.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Only the best submission by each participating team will be considered. We will use the well-established rank-then-aggregate strategy as the ranking scheme.

Step 1 (Compute): For each test case, we will compute the Interaction Efficacy (DSC @last: higher = better, FPV @last: lower = better, FNV @last: lower = better) and the Interaction Utilization (AUC-DSC: higher = better,

AUC-FPV: lower = better, AUC-FNV: lower = better) metrics, producing 6 metrics per test case.

Step 2 (Rank): Separate rankings will be computed for each of the 6 metrics on each test case.

Step 3 (Aggregate): The final rank for each team will be computed as the aggregation (mean) of the (6 x N) ranks over the N test cases.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions with missing results on test cases will not be considered for the leader board.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The described ranking system was used to reflect the specific challenges of the underlying task. On the one hand, it is important to accurately segment tumor lesions; on the other hand, the specific challenge of this task is to avoid false positive segmentations of physiological tracer uptake. In addition the tumor should be detected with as minimal additional user annotated information as possible. If accurate segmentation cannot be achieved, we are interested in measuring the algorithm's performance on detecting the lesions.

The rank-then-aggregate strategy was chosen because it provides a robust and fair framework for evaluating and comparing the performance of models across diverse test cases and metrics. This method has been well-established in the evaluation of segmentation challenges, ensuring consistency and reproducibility in the ranking process. By separating evaluation into distinct steps — computing metrics, ranking teams for each metric, and aggregating results — this approach mitigates potential biases arising from differences in scale or distribution between metrics (DSC, FPV, FNV) which we have observed in previous iterations of the autoPET challenge. The use of ranking normalizes performance comparisons, making them less sensitive to outliers or variations in absolute metric values across test cases.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

For each submission, mean and standard deviation over the test cohort and range of the defined metrics will be computed.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

These statistical methods will be used in order to provide an overview of algorithm performance and reliability under changing inputs (additional user interactions).

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,

- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Inference runtime of algorithms and in-detail performance analysis for domain shifts (imaging site, lesion location, volume, pathology, tracer, ...) of each algorithm which we will publish in the manuscript after challenge completion.

TASK 2: CT lesion segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Please see Task 1

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

CT, Tumor, Segmentation, Detection

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Thomas Küstner (University Hospital Tübingen)

Felix Peisen (University Hospital Tübingen)

Sergios Gatidis (University Hospital Tübingen)

Andreas Wagner (University Hospital Tübingen)

Ornela Megne (University Hospital Tübingen)

Ahmed Othman (University Hospital Mainz)

Antoine Sanner (University Hospital Mainz)

Tanja Loßau (Fraunhofer MEVIS)

Jan Hendrik Moltz (Fraunhofer MEVIS)

Temke Kohlbrandt (Fraunhofer MEVIS)

Zdravko Marinov (KIT Karlsruhe)

Alessa Hering (Radboud University Medical Center)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Küstner

University Hospital Tübingen

72076 Tübingen, Germany

E-mail: thomas.kuestner@med.uni-tuebingen.de

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some

modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event as open call challenge

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge website will be opened on grand-challenge (similar to the previous challenges: autopet.grand-challenge.org)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic, Interactive

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We foresee the following awards for the best submissions in

Category 2: Lesion segmentation in longitudinal CT

1st Place: 3,000 €

2nd Place: 2,000 €

3rd Place: 1,000 €

In the event of a tie the aggregate prize allocated for the tied positions shall be combined and equitably divided among the participants who share the identical ranking.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submissions will be reported in the leaderboard. Participating teams can opt out of publication of their results in the leaderboard. Prize-winning methods will be announced publicly as part of a scientific session at the MICCAI annual meeting.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The prize-winning teams will be invited to contribute to draft and submit a manuscript describing the methods and results of the challenge in a peer-reviewed journal. The first and last author of the prize-winning submissions will be also listed as authors of this planned manuscript. The participating teams may publish their own results separately after coordination to avoid significant overlap with the challenge paper.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be accepted as Docker containers according to the technical requirements of grand-challenge.org. Submission details will be published at the time point of challenge announcement.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

In order to enable participants to assess the technical compatibility of their to-be-submitted algorithm, we will provide information on successful algorithm deployment upon submission. To this end, the submitted algorithms will be applied to a small number of test data ensuring technical compatibility. This will allow participants to resubmit their algorithms in case of technical failure.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)

- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge announcement and release of training cases: 03/2025

Registration: starting 04/2025

Submission deadline: 09/2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

For the newly released CT data: The challenge dataset will be released in an anonymized fashion on a public accessible archive (for example Zenodo). The ethics committee of the University Hospital Tuebingen was consulted regarding anonymized publication of training data. Ethical approval was obtained for the anonymized training database.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code for algorithm evaluation together with a script for standardized user interaction simulation and pre-simulated clicks will be available at the time point of challenge submission on:

www.github.com/lab-midas/autoPETCTIV

We will furthermore provide two trained baseline models and the code for creating the grand-challenge Docker containers.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Publication of algorithm code will be a prerequisite for award eligibility. To this end, code will need to be published on a publicly accessible repository of the teams choice within a week after submission deadline.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge is an initiative of the Radiology Departments of the University Hospitals of Tuebingen and Mainz together with Fraunhofer MEVIS. The challenge will also be advertised in the European Society of Radiology (ESR) and the European Society for Hybrid, Molecular and Translational Imaging (ESHI-MT). We have secured funding for this challenge at BMBF (German Federal Ministry of Education and Research). We aim to additionally seek funding for this challenge from major companies in the field of medical imaging and data analysis. So far, no concrete sponsoring has been agreed on. Test cases and labels will only be available to a limited number of colleagues involved in organizing this challenge at the participating institutions.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Research, Screening, Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization

- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection, Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of patients undergoing longitudinal CT screening examinations in an oncologic context for diagnosis, staging, or therapy response assessment, from multiple imaging sites.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The CT cohort comprises whole-body imaging in 333 patients (female: 170, mean age: 64y, std age: 15y) of two imaging timepoints: baseline staging, and follow-up scans after therapy treatment. Training data was acquired at a single site (UKT), while test data comprises a multi-site setting (UKT and Mainz). Additional information about the CT imaging protocol is provided in the section "Data acquisition details".

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All CT data within this challenge have been acquired on state-of-the-art CT scanners using standardized protocols following international guidelines. CT data are provided as 3D volumes consisting of stacks of axial slices.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information will be provided regarding the image data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Age, sex, diagnosis

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target and challenge cohort depict targeted CT imaging regions over a whole-body range. Usually, the scan range of these examinations extends from the skull base to the mid-thigh level. If clinically relevant, scans can be extended to cover the entire body including the entire head and legs/feet.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target structures of the to-be-developed algorithms are malignant tumors (i.e. primary tumors and metastases).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT data were acquired on state-of-the-art CT scanners (Siemens Sensation 64, Siemens SOMATOM Definition AS, Siemens SOMATOM Definition Flash, Siemens SOMATOM Force) and on a PET/CT scanner (Siemens Biograph128).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Training data:

Patients were scanned with the inhouse whole-body staging protocol for a scan field from skull base to the middle of the femur with patients laid in a supine position, arms raised above the head. Scanning was performed during the portal-venous phase after administration of body-weight adapted contrast medium through the cubital vein. Attenuation-based tube current modulation (CARE Dose, reference mAs 240) and tube voltage (120 kV) were applied. The following scan parameters were used:

SOMATOM Force: collimation 128 × 0.6 mm, rotation time 0.5 s, pitch 0.6.

Sensation64: collimation 64×0.6 mm, rotation time 0.5 s, pitch 0.6

SOMATOM Definition Flash: collimation 128×0.6 mm, rotation time 0.5 s, pitch 1.0

SOMATOM Definition AS: collimation 64×0.6 mm, rotation time 0.5 s, pitch 0.6

Biograph128: collimation 128×0.6 mm, rotation time 0.5 s, pitch 0.8

Slice thickness as well as increment were set to 3 mm. A medium smooth kernel was used for image reconstruction.

Test data: Test data will be drawn in part (50%) from the same sources and distributions as the training data. The other part will be drawn from another center: University Hospital Mainz (50%). At this moment we will not disclose details of the test data as we aim to avoid fine-tuning of algorithms to the test data domain. The distribution of test data will be made public after the challenge deadline.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data were acquired from two large university hospitals (UKT, Mainz).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data were acquired by specialized teams consisting of radiologists and technologists. Manual segmentation of tumor lesions was performed by three experienced radiologists (two for training dataset and two for test dataset).

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case (training or test case) consists of one 3D CT volume, and one 3D binary mask of manually segmented tumor lesions on the CT volume, in two imaging sessions/time points: baseline and follow-up after therapy treatment.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training cases: 333 CT studies of two imaging time points: baseline and follow-up.

Test cases: 160 CT studies (80 UKT, 80 Mainz) of two imaging time points: baseline and follow-up.

Challenge participants are free to use additional external training data or pre-trained models as long as these are publicly available. If additional labels are generated in this process, these should be made publicly available by the

participants after the challenge. The use of additional training data or models should be reported.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The number of training cases is a trade-off between the effort of manual lesion segmentation and the necessity for sufficient training data. It provides a large publicly available labeled CT dataset of whole-body regions in two imaging time points (baseline and follow-up).

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All training cases are drawn from a single hospital: University Hospital Tuebingen (UKT)

Test cases are drawn from two hospitals: University Hospital Tuebingen (UKT), University Hospital Mainz (Mainz) with each site providing 80 cases.

The rationale behind this selection of test cases is to assess the robustness of algorithms under therapies and to cross-evaluate the effects of centers.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Data of 333 cases (i.e. 100%) will be released for training as part of the proposed challenge. 160 cases (i.e. 100%) of two centers will be formed for testing of algorithm performances.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

All data were manually annotated by two experienced radiologists. To this end, tumor lesions were manually segmented on the CT image data using dedicated software.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The following annotation protocol was defined:

Step 1: Identification of tumor lesions by visual assessment of CT information together with the clinical examination reports.

Step 2: Manual free-hand segmentation of identified lesions in axial slices.

Step 3: Baseline and follow-up segmentations are viewed side-by-side to mark the matching lesions.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

CT training data was annotated by a radiologist with 8 years of experience and reviewed by a radiologist with 4 years of experience.

CT test data from UKT was annotated by a radiologist (UKT) with 8 years of experience and reviewed by a

radiologist (Mainz) with 4 years of experience. Vice versa, data from Mainz was annotated by a radiologist (Mainz) with 14 years of experience and reviewed by a radiologist (UKT) with 8 years of experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For training and test data, original DICOM files will be anonymized and provided. In addition, scripts for conversion to the NIfTI format will be provided.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

One relevant possible error source for image annotation is the uncertainty of tumour delineation. In some cases the differentiation between malignant and benign tissue can be difficult. Moreover, the alignment of tumors between the follow-up imaging sessions can be challenging in some cases.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

A further potential error source are image artifacts in CT that may result in altered image properties.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will use a combination of 6 metrics reflecting the aims and specific challenges for the task of CT lesion detection and segmentation, that are formed of three basic measures:

a) Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) of segmented lesions (equal to F1 Score).

b) False positive volumes (FPV): Volume of false positive connected components that do not overlap with positives.

c) False negative volumes (FNV): Volume of false negative connected components that do not overlap with true positives.

resulting in:

1) DSC @last: Interaction Efficacy of DSC with given lesion center in follow-up scan (similar to last interactive segmentation step in Task 1).

- 2) FPV @last: Interaction Efficacy of FPV with given lesion center in follow-up scan (similar to last interactive segmentation step in Task 1).
- 3) FNV @last: Interaction Efficacy of FNV with given lesion center in follow-up scan (similar to last interactive segmentation step in Task 1).
- 4) DSC @init: Interaction Efficacy of DSC without given lesion center in follow-up scan.
- 5) FPV @init: Interaction Efficacy of FPV without given lesion center in follow-up scan.
- 6) FNV @init: Interaction Efficacy of FNV without given lesion center in follow-up scan.

DSC, FPV, and FNV will be evaluated with (metrics 1-3) and without (metrics 4-6) standardized and pre-simulated tumor lesion center click in the follow-up scan (one click per lesion). The lesion center click is represented as a set of 3D coordinates matching the input image.

In case of test data that do not contain positives (no lesions), only metric 2 and 5 will be used.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The overarching objective of the present challenge is to develop approaches for tumor lesion segmentations in follow-up scans given a baseline segmentation. We identified this step as a critical measure towards a more objective and quantitative image analysis. While the impact of such a quantitative approach on clinical decision-making is far beyond the scope of the present challenge, we have devised our metrics for the challenge to reflect the critical aspect of CT tumor detection under various levels of user interaction/segmentation. It can be expected that some simplistic annotations are available, or can be provided by the user to adjust or guide the algorithm performance. We are interested in exploring the algorithm's dependency on such information and how additional label information could potentially improve the performance.

The post-challenge analysis of the previous iterations of the autoPET challenge showed that the three basic measures (DSC, FPV, FNV) provide a comprehensive summary description of algorithm performance in terms of segmentation accuracy. In addition, these measures have been used and validated in the previous iterations of the challenge, hence enabling a direct comparison of the proposed challenge with previous iterations. The Dice score will be used as a measure of overall segmentation performance. False positive and false negative volumes are used to reflect the specific challenges of lesion segmentation, such as identifying not well delineated lesions and detecting small tumor lesions.

Ad 1-6) Interaction efficacy assesses the quality of the final segmentation achieved after a predefined annotation budget, in this case for a provided center lesion click. It ensures that the model can deliver high-quality results within a practical and constrained amount of user interaction. This is crucial for real-world usability, where the ability to produce accurate and clinically meaningful segmentations without exceeding a reasonable annotation effort can significantly enhance workflow efficiency and reduce the burden on clinicians.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Only the best submission by each participating team will be considered. We will use the well-established rank-then-aggregate strategy as the ranking scheme.

Step 1 (Compute): For each test case, we will compute the Interaction Efficacy with (DSC @last: higher = better, FPV @last: lower = better, FNV @last: lower = better) and without (DSC @init: higher = better, FPV @init: lower = better, FNV @init: lower = better) provided center lesion click, producing 6 metrics per test case.

Step 2 (Rank): Separate rankings will be computed for each of the 6 metrics on each test case.

Step 3 (Aggregate): The final rank for each team will be computed as the aggregation (mean) of the (6 x N) ranks over the N test cases.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions with missing results on test cases will not be considered for the leader board.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The described ranking system was used to reflect the specific challenges of the underlying task. On the one hand, it is important to accurately segment tumor lesions; on the other hand, the specific challenge of this task is to avoid false positive segmentations of not well delineated lesions. In addition the tumor should be detected with as minimal additional user annotated information as possible. If accurate segmentation cannot be achieved, we are interested in measuring the algorithm's performance on detecting the lesions.

The rank-then-aggregate strategy was chosen because it provides a robust and fair framework for evaluating and comparing the performance of models across diverse test cases and metrics. This method has been well-established in the evaluation of segmentation challenges, ensuring consistency and reproducibility in the ranking process. By separating evaluation into distinct steps — computing metrics, ranking teams for each metric, and aggregating results — this approach mitigates potential biases arising from differences in scale or distribution between metrics (DSC, FPV, FNV) which we have observed in previous iterations of the autoPET challenge. The use of ranking normalizes performance comparisons, making them less sensitive to outliers or variations in absolute metric values across test cases.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

For each submission, mean and standard deviation over the test cohort and range of the defined metrics will be computed.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

These statistical methods will be used in order to provide an overview of algorithm performance and reliability under changing inputs (additional user interactions).

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Inference runtime of algorithms and in-detail performance analysis for domain shifts (lesion location, volume, ...) of each algorithm which we will publish in the manuscript after challenge completion.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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<https://github.com/lab-midas/autoPET>

<https://autopet.grand-challenge.org/>

<https://autopet-ii.grand-challenge.org/>

<https://autopet-iii.grand-challenge.org/>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A